

Comparing band-stop and broadband noise absorbers for non-uniform inflow propellers

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With the advent of urban air mobility and distributed electric propulsion in aviation, the need for effective noise mitigation strategies for propeller systems has become pressing. The presently-reported study concerned the application of noise-mitigating materials, in the bottom wall of the UTwente's wind-tunnel test section, underneath a non-shrouded propeller subject to a non-uniform inflow. The objective was to experimentally assess the noise mitigating materials impact on tonal noise reduction, emitted noise levels, and sound-emission directivity. Two types of noise-mitigating materials were applied: arrays of additive-manufactured quarter-wavelength resonators and a slab of porous material (metal foam). In the case of the quarter-wavelength resonators, the effect of several geometrical configurations on noise reduction was investigated. An optimal configuration was found; viz., with the cells of the quarter-wavelength oscillator arrays distributed everywhere on the instrumentation surface, except right underneath the propeller blades. Indeed, it was observed that applying quarter-wavelength resonators immediately underneath the propeller in combination with a critical clearance induces a spurious hydrodynamic interaction, which amplifies the propeller's tonal noise. The latter is markedly true for higher harmonics. In addition, the quarter-wavelength resonators' performance was compared to a flat plate (reference) and the metal foam (broadband absorber). Findings show that the efficiency of the quarter-wavelength-resonator solution is highly dependent on the configuration. Moreover, the tuned-quarter-wavelength-resonator outperformed the broadband porous material in noise reduction. The polar directivity of the recorded emitted sound is affected by the configuration. It was found that the presence of any sound-mitigating material underneath the propeller, is consistently detrimental to the azimuthal directivity.

Nomenclature

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D	=	propeller diameter, m
f_l	=	lower-bound cutoff frequency, Hz
f_u	=	upper-bound cutoff frequency, Hz
H	=	form factor
J	=	advance ratio, $U_\infty/(n \cdot D)$
n	=	rotational speed, Hz
p_t	=	time-domain pressure signal, Pa
p_{ref}	=	reference pressure, Pa
p_{rms}	=	root-mean-square of pressure data, Pa
P	=	power spectral density of the signal, Pa ²
Re_x	=	Reynolds number based on X, XU_∞/ν
Re_{δ_2}	=	Reynolds number for the momentum thickness, $\delta_2 U_\infty/\nu$
U_∞	=	flow speed, m · s ⁻¹
X	=	streamwise distance from the tripping device, m
x	=	streamwise coordinate, m
y	=	spanwise coordinate, m
z	=	vertical coordinate, m
β	=	Clouser parameter
δ	=	boundary layer thickness, m
δ_1	=	displacement thickness, m
δ_2	=	momentum thickness, m
θ	=	polar angle, °
ν	=	kinematic viscosity of air, m ² · s ⁻¹
ϕ	=	azimuthal angle, °

I. Introduction

Reduction of noise generated by propeller systems poses a significant challenge for emerging aviation concepts, such as urban air mobility (UAM) and distributed electric propulsion (DEP) designs [1–3]. Those concepts usually entail multi-propulsion designs, leading to interactions between the propulsive system and the airframe. Moreover, propellers are commonly the preferred propulsion mechanism for the above-mentioned innovative designs for its low-speed efficiency in comparison with reaction propulsion concepts [4].

The noise mechanisms associated with propeller-airframe interactions have been studied quite extensively. Pre-

viously reported experimental results [5–8] consistently show a significant increase in noise levels when propellers interact with turbulence or boundary layers. Additionally, these studies highlight the tendency of haystacking on low-frequency noise due to the blade interaction with turbulence in large-scale structures. Consequently, a noise reduction solution for those propeller-airframe interactions is necessary to avoid the detrimental noise increase of those innovative aircraft designs.

Although extensive research has been dedicated to noise mitigation strategies at the blade design level [9, 10] and the application of acoustic liners for shrouded propellers [11, 12], passive noise-mitigation strategies for un-ducted propellers have not received the same attention. Therefore, with an emerging interest in/application of BLI, a need to study the influence of passive noise-mitigation strategies was identified.

In this context, the EU-funded ENODISE (Enabling Optimized DisruptivE airframe propulsion-integration concepts) project aimed to help reduce aircraft noise emissions by systematically investigating generic propeller-airframe integration configurations. The presently-presented work aimed to investigate acoustic-abatement strategies in a controlled lab-setting applied to generic propeller-airframe configurations.

Coupled quarter-wavelength resonators (QWRs) have proven to be particularly efficient for noise absorption [13, 14]. One of their advantages is that they make manipulating porosity and the absorption frequency range relatively straightforward [13, 14]. Boulvert et al. [13] studied folded QWRs. They reported quasi-perfect noise absorption and a good agreement between experimental and numerical results [13]. Shen et al. [14] investigated the sound-absorption effect of multiple neighboring QWRs numerically and experimentally, finding that the mutual impedance of multiple QWRs is an essential factor in the absorption of coupled QWRs.

When noise-mitigating materials are applied, the level of emitted noise is affected by factors like the material's porosity, absorption frequency, and its distance from the source of the noise [15–17]. Palleja-Cabre et al. [16, 17] conducted studies on over-tip liners for tip-leakage noise reduction. Their findings highlight that the noise-mitigating material's porosity and positioning relative to the blade tip affect noise reduction [16, 17]. Gorny and Koopman [15] investigated QWRs for tonal-noise control in shrouded fans. Using different patterns of QWR arrays on the inner walls of a ducted rotor's shroud, they showed that considerably reducing the tonal noise levels is possible. Additionally, Gorny and Koopman [15] showed the importance of the resonator's configuration in the emitted noise directivity.

The primary objective of the research reported in this paper was to experimentally assess the effect of purpose-built noise-mitigating materials installed in a flat plate beneath a propeller on emitted sound levels and directivity. Two noise-mitigating materials were used in the presently-reported study: a band-stop mitigator consisting of tuned QWRs and a porous metal acting as a broadband sound absorber. Different configurations of the QWRs distribution underneath the propeller were studied.

In section II, the experimental methodology and a description of the experimental means are provided. The results of the study are presented and discussed in section III. Conclusions are drawn in section IV.

II. Experimental Approach

A. Experimental setup

The measurements were conducted in the UTwente’s aeroacoustic wind tunnel, a closed-loop system. An anechoic chamber encloses its test section. This test section has a rectangular cross-section of $0.7 \times 0.9 \text{ m}^2$. The wind tunnel can generate airflow speeds of up to $60 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ within the test section while maintaining turbulence-intensity below 0.08% [18]. The enclosing anechoic chamber, of $6 \times 6 \times 4 \text{ m}^3$, is lined with commercially available sound-absorbing wedges on the walls and additional absorbers on other surfaces. Its cut-off frequency is 160 Hz.

A sketch of the experimental setup used to investigate the influence of noise-mitigating materials on emitted noise is shown in Fig. 1. The coordinates system is defined as follows: x and y are the streamwise and spanwise coordinates (origin at the center of the propeller), and z is the vertical coordinate (origin at the flat plate).

A propeller and its propulsive system were placed downstream from the wind tunnel test section’s inlet close to the bottom of the test section. The propeller clearance (distance between the blade tip and flat plate) could be varied using a traverse system. At the test section’s inlet, 3.62 m upstream from the propeller’s plane, an 8 mm-high zigzag tripping device was installed to trigger the development of a turbulent boundary layer. As detailed in the introduction (§I), quantifying the influence of turbulent-boundary-layer parameters on the emitted sound was particularly of interest.

The propeller that was used in the current study was a 2-bladed Meijzlik 12” \times 18” ($D = 304.8 \text{ mm}$). The project *SilentProp* provides details regarding its geometry and can be found in Ref. [19]. Information about the propulsive system and the propeller baseline-noise characteristics can be found in [20].

Fig. 1 Schematics of the experimental setup.

B. Far-field acoustic Setup

To record the noise emitted by the propeller and the flat plate below it, two microphone arrays were used: a concave array mounted directly overhead of the propeller (polar plane) and a straight linear array positioned on the left-hand

side of the propeller (azimuthal plane). In this text, said linear array will also be referred to as the side array. Both arrays were oriented parallel to the main-flow direction. The microphone arrays were used to quantify directivity and emitted sound levels. The two microphone arrays were instrumented as follows: the concave array had 17 mounted microphones, and the linear array had nine microphones mounted on it.

The overhead array was affixed to a rod, which protruded from the anechoic chambers' ceiling, so the central microphone was directly above the propeller. The authors defined this central microphone to be at a polar angle of 90° . On either side of this central microphone, eight microphones were fixed, forming a polar angle, referred to through the text as θ , ranging from 40° (upstream side) to 135° (downstream side).

The linear microphone array was positioned on the left-hand side of the propeller, instrumented with nine microphones. The microphone in the middle—i.e., the fifth with respect to either end—was aligned with the propeller's plane at an azimuthal angle ϕ of 90° . The distance from the propeller to the central microphone was 1.50 m (4.92 D; see Fig. 1b). This array allowed one to investigate the emitted sound's directivity in the range: 55° (upstream) 125° (downstream).

The microphones used were GRAS 40PH-10. The acquisition was made using NI PXIe-4499 modules installed in a NI PXIe-1073 chassis. All microphone data acquisition was performed with an acquisition time of 30 s and acquisition frequency of 2^{16} Hz. The microphones' sensitivity was calibrated using a GRAS 40AG piston-phone (94 dB, 1 kHz) before the measurements. Moreover, after each set of experiments was completed, said sensitivity was checked using the piston-phone mentioned above.

C. Noise-mitigating strategies

Considering the absorption of sound waves emanating from the propeller and impinging on the surface below it, samples of noise-mitigation materials could be flush-mounted underneath the propeller—in the test section's bottom wall as shown in Fig. 1a. Two different materials were used as samples for this mitigation strategy: sets of quarter-wavelength resonator arrays (acting as a band-stop noise absorber) and a commercially available metal foam (broadband noise absorber).

1. Quarter-wavelength oscillator

Van der Eerden's [21] low reduced-frequency model for coupled prisms was used to design band-stop noise-absorbing components. Said components are referred to as QWR-cell or QWR-array in this work. The model, which is Helmholtz-equation-based, considers viscous and thermal effects and assesses sound propagation within prismatic tubes. The model is applicable within specific ranges of reduced frequency and shear-wave number, considering the ratio of the tube length to the acoustic wavelength. The model quantifies sound absorption and reflection by a QWR array. Indeed, by setting the number of tubes and tube length in a QWR array, it is possible to tune the porosity and

frequency range of absorption.

For the current study, each QWR-array was a rectangle with a $0.05 \times 0.05 \text{ m}^2$ open-face area. Each array contained 49 tubes of different lengths where each individual tube is a QWR. The tubes had 2.75 mm radii, resulting in a 47% porosity. The arrays were designed so that the frequency range between $f = 800 \text{ Hz}$ and $f = 1200 \text{ Hz}$ would be optimally absorbed. Analytical and experimental results for the absorption coefficient of the units are presented in §III.A.

2. Porous material

The porous material used in the experiments was a $0.33 \times 0.33 \text{ m}^2$ high-porosity iron foam (88% porosity) and small pore size (35 PPI). The thickness of the piece was 15 mm. It was applied as a broadband-noise absorber on the surface underneath the propeller.

Previous research applied this metal foam for hydrodynamic absorption and flow penetration experimental studies [22].

3. Measurement of the noise absorption by the QWRs and porous metal

Before they were applied as noise mitigators, as described in §II.C, the acoustics materials were characterized by means of an impedance tube.

The impedance tube used in the analysis of the samples is a 1026 mm long, 50 mm diameter tube, with a VISATON FRS 6.5 cm full-range speaker. White noise is swept from 50 Hz to 5 kHz at one end of the tube. Subsequently, the initial wave and the reflected wave are captured by two fixed GRAS 40 PH microphones. The absorption coefficient of the tube end is determined using the transfer function method [23].

The absorption performance of the noise-mitigating materials was assessed averaging the impedance-tube results of five different samples of both a QWR-cell and the metal foam

D. Test Conditions

1. Propeller tests without flow

To examine the interaction between the propeller blades and the QWR, experiments were conducted without wind-tunnel-imposed flow ($U_\infty = 0 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, referred to as the 'static condition'). Unless stated otherwise, the propeller was operated at 6000 RPM with a 5-mm clearance.

2. Investigation of the QWR-configuration effect on far-field noise

A number of different spatial combinations of QWR-cells and flat-reflective surfaces was used to investigate the influence of the QWR-cell configuration on recorded noise and its directivity. The various investigated QWR-cell configurations implemented on the $30 \times 30 \text{ cm}^2$ instrumentation surface underneath the propeller (1b) are shown in

Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Top view of the QWR-cells configurations. White squares represent the flat plates and perforated squares represent the QWR-cell units. In red, as reference, the position of the propeller is shown.

Additionally, an experiment was carried out to quantify the background noise generated by the presence of the QWR, subject to a wind-tunnel-imposed flow. This test aimed to: quantify whether the mere presence of the QWRs contributes significantly to the recorded sound in the experiments with wind-tunnel-imposed flow. To this end, in the absence of a propeller and its propulsive system, the background noise of the wind tunnel with the flat plate and with the full-QWR was recorded.

3. Comparison between metal foam and QWRs

By analyzing the results in terms of noise mitigation and directivity changes in both arrays, the optimal band-stop QWR configuration was determined. The results obtained with said optimal QWR configuration were compared to those obtained with the commercially-available metal foam installed underneath the propeller (covering the whole of the $33 \times 33 \text{ cm}^2$ instrumentation surface).

E. Data processing

1. Spectral analysis

The experiments' primary objective is to present noise level results, facilitating a comparative analysis of different noise mitigation strategies. Consequently, data processing was centered on extracting sound pressure levels from the acquired time-domain pressure signal p_t . The most prevalent methods for representing these noise levels include the

Sound Pressure Level (SPL), which illustrates their distribution across frequencies, and the Overall Sound Pressure Level (OSPL), indicating the absolute noise level across the entire frequency spectrum.

The recorded signals' post-processing was performed through spectral analysis. In particular, the Welch method was applied, with a 50%-overlap Hanning window, and a block size of 2^{14} (0.250 s) samples, which resulted in a frequency resolution of 4 Hz.

The results for Sound Pressure Level (SPL) are shown in terms of frequency using Eq. 1, where the power spectral density of the signal is given by $P(f)$, and the equation is normalized for $p_{\text{ref}} = 20 \mu\text{Pa}/\sqrt{Hz}$.

$$\text{SPL} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{P(f)}{P_{\text{ref}}^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the overall sound pressure level (OSPL) is computed using the frequency domain definition [24] (Eq. 2), where f_l is a lower-bound cutoff frequency and f_u is an upper-bound cutoff frequency.

$$\text{OSPL} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \int_{f_l}^{f_u} \frac{P(f)}{P_{\text{ref}}^2} df, \quad (2)$$

For the current experiments, the results for OSPL were calculated for a lower-bound cutoff frequency of 160 Hz (cutoff frequency of the wind tunnel (§ II.A)). Given that there is no background noise contamination as the recorded signal's levels are above 3 dB with respect to the background noise (see §III.B.1), the upper-bound cutoff frequency was chosen to be the maximum frequency of the signal.

Additionally, quantifying the differences in overall sound pressure levels between configurations is of interest. To do this, the authors define ΔOSPL as follows:

$$\Delta\text{OSPL} = \text{OSPL}_{\text{mit}} - \text{OSPL}_{\text{ref}} \quad (3)$$

In the case of this study the reference is the full-flat-plate configuration. When positive ΔOSPL indicates a noise-level increase. Negative values of ΔOSPL indicate noise abatement.

F. Test section flow velocity accuracy

The accuracy of the flow velocity measurement was determined by using error propagation and manufacturer's data-sheet information. The measurements of the pitot tube (to know: the dynamic pressure Δp , the static pressure p_s and the flow temperature T_0) the velocity of the free stream is $U_{\infty} = 30 \pm 0.66 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$

III. Results

A. Impedance-tube test results

In Fig. 3, the acoustic-absorption properties of a QWR-cell are shown, determined using an impedance tube (see §II.C.3). The finely-dotted line is the analytical result for the low reduced-frequency model (§ II.C.1). For comparison, the results for a flat-plate termination are shown (red line).

The data for the QWR, in the range 700 Hz to 1200 Hz, is in relatively good agreement with the analytical model. However, these experimental results are preliminary in nature. The authors note e.g. the QWR sample used to obtain these results did not neatly fit in the impedance tube, which resulted in leakage. This issue will be resolved. Additionally, the authors plan to carry out impedance-tube measurements of the porous material used in the wind-tunnel experiments (See §III.B.4).

Fig. 3 Absorption coefficient as a function of frequency for a QWR-cell unit.

B. Wind tunnel test results

1. Acoustic measurements of the background noise with and without the QWR

Before performing experiments with a propeller and an imposed flow, it is necessary to check for any influence of the imposed flow with the QWR-cells. The following results are for the case without the propeller and the propulsive system, with the QWR-cells installed (full-QWR configuration, Fig. 2a) and a wind-tunnel-imposed flow ($U_\infty = 30 \pm 0.66 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$). An analogous experiment with only the flat plate was done as a reference.

In Fig. 4, two cases are compared: with (solid grey line) and without (finely-dotted black line) the application of QWR-cells. One notes a slight increase in recorded noise in the range between 600 Hz and 3000 Hz, when the QWR cells are applied. However, the presence of said cells does not cause resonant peaks. Therefore, one can exclude flow-QWR interaction as a mechanism that leads to tonal peaks in spectra obtained in experiments that involve a rotating propeller and wind-tunnel-imposed flow—the results of which are discussed in the following subsections. Moreover, the background noise levels are less than 3 dB of the propeller noise, ensuring that there is no influence of

the background noise of the wind tunnel with the propeller noise experiments.

Fig. 4 Background noise of the QWR fully applied (gray line) and flat plate (dotted line), without propeller installed ($U_\infty = 30 \pm 0.66 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, microphone at $\theta = 90^\circ$).

2. Effect of clearance on the QWR performance

The influence of the clearance on the hydrodynamic effect caused by the passage of the propeller-blade tips over the QWR-cells is addressed in this section. Two cases are considered: without ($U_\infty = 0 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) and with ($U_\infty = 30 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) wind-tunnel-imposed flow. In both cases, the QWR-cell configuration was the so-called full-QWR configuration (Fig. 2a), and the propeller rotation speed was 6000 RPM — resulting in an advance ratio $J = 0.98$, close to the peak efficiency of the propeller.

In Fig. 5 spectra are shown for the $U_\infty = 0$ case. These spectra were recorded using three different microphones of the arc: the central overhead microphone ($\theta = 90^\circ$), the most upstream microphone at ($\theta = 40^\circ$), and the most downstream microphone ($\theta = 135^\circ$). Experiments with two different clearances were performed to determine the effect of the clearance between the propeller and the QWRs: 5 mm (solid red line) and 20 mm (solid grey line). The finely-dotted black line in Fig. 5 shows the spectra without any QWRs (flat plate, 5 mm clearance) and serves as a reference spectra.

One observes in the 5 mm-clearance case: significantly more pronounced tonal noise in higher harmonics (Fig. 5). Moreover, in the frequency range from 750 Hz to 1650 Hz (zoomed in graphs on the left), one also observes an increase in tonal noise. That was unexpected given that this is the frequency range for which the QWR was designed for optimal sound absorption (see Fig. 3).

A second test was conducted to determine if this unexpected effect depends on the clearance. The clearance was set to 20 mm, and all other parameters remained constant. The results of this test are indicated with a solid grey line in Fig. 5. Each row shows the spectra for a different microphone angle: most upstream ($\theta = 40^\circ$); central microphone ($\theta = 90^\circ$) and most downstream ($\theta = 135^\circ$). The first column shows the whole spectra. The second column shows

the zoom in the frequency range of interest. One notes that the results do not display the above-discussed effects found for a clearance of 5 mm, especially for higher harmonics.

Considering there was no imposed flow, the authors suspected that the increase of the tonal peaks and the significantly more pronounced higher harmonics found for a clearance of 5 mm is due to a local hydrodynamic effect. Tests were conducted with varied configurations of the QWR-unit cells to confirm this suspicion. They were installed in the instrumentation plate underneath the propeller, and all configurations had no QWR-cell directly underneath the propeller's center (2); in this case, the aforementioned hydrodynamic interaction does not manifest. The results of said additional tests can be found in §III.B.3.

Fig. 5 Noise spectra of the propeller on different clearance distances from the full-QWR configuration with no forward flow ($U_\infty = 0 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$). Propeller at 6000 RPM.

In Fig. 6 results for $U_\infty = 30 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, clearances of 5 mm (solid red line) and 20 mm (solid grey line) are shown. Not only does one observe what the authors infer to be the same effect found for the $U_\infty = 0$ case, but one can clearly see that in this case, there is an even more marked effect on higher harmonics.

In Fig. 7a, the overall sound pressure levels (OSPL) measured using the overhead microphone array are shown as a function of the polar angle θ . Three cases are examined: the flat-plate case (no noise-mitigating material was applied),

Fig. 6 Noise spectra of the propeller on different clearance distances for the full-QWR configuration with forward flow ($U_\infty = 30 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$). Propeller at 6000 RPM.

the 5 mm-clearance case, and the 20 mm-clearance case. One observes that for the 5 mm-clearance case, noise levels are overall highest. This is particularly clear in Fig. 7b, where the sound pressure level difference ΔOSPL (Eq. 3) to the flat-plate reference case is shown. Indeed, one discerns a sound-pressure-level increase as high as 3 dB at some points. In addition, one notices that the clearance affects the directivity, although this effect is less pronounced for the microphones covering the range $80^\circ \leq \theta \leq 100^\circ$.

The results obtained with the linear array, located on the left-hand side of the propeller in the stream-wise direction, seem to, across all azimuthal angles, display a structural increase in emitted sound pressure levels towards the upstream angles, although the 20-mm clearance case shows reduced noise levels compared to the 5-mm case.

Fig. 7 Overhead directivity for 5-mm (red-line-connected squares) and 20-mm (grey-line-connected circles) clearances ($U_\infty = 30 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, 6000 RPM). (a) Directivity. (b) Comparison between results for $h = 5$ mm, $h = 20$ mm and flat plate.

Fig. 8 Side array directivity for 5-mm and 20-mm clearances ($U_\infty = 30 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, 6000 RPM). (a) Directivity. (b) Comparison between the full-flat-plate case and $h = 5$ mm, $h = 20$ mm, respectively

3. Influence of QWR-cell configuration

To confirm the author's hypothesis that the occurrence of increased tonal peaks for a clearance of 5 mm, described in §III.B.2, is a local hydrodynamic effect, additional tests were performed. Moreover, the general aim of said tests was to quantify the influence of QWR-cell configuration on emitted noise—in the range for which the QWR was designed to optimally absorb sound—and find the optimal configuration for this particular noise mitigation technique. In Fig. 2 (II.D.2), the investigated QWR-cell configurations are shown. Going forward, these configurations will be referred to as: full-QWR (Fig. 2a), flat-plate-center (Fig. 2b), flat-plate-blade (Fig. 2c), downstream-only (Fig. 2d), and upstream-only (Fig. 2e). The reference case is the full-flat-plate case (Fig. 2f).

In Fig. 9, recorded spectra obtained with an overhead microphone at $\theta = 90^\circ$, $U_\infty = 30 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and a propeller rotating at 6000 RPM are shown for the following configurations: flat-plate-center (Fig. 9a), flat-plate-blade (Fig. 9b),

downstream-only (Fig. 9c), and upstream-only (Fig. 9d). The results are compared to the full-flat-plate case (finely-dotted grey line), the case where one has not applied any QWR-cell, and the instrumentation plate is essentially a hard wall. Moreover, the following discussion compares the results to the so-called full-QWR configuration (Fig. 6).

One observes in Fig. 9a that for the flat-plate-center case, the tonal increase is less pronounced than was observed in Fig. 6 for the full-QWR configuration. That said, the emitted noise levels are overall higher than the configuration with no QWRs (finely-dotted black line). As one can appreciate in Fig. 9b, when the blade area is completely covered with flat plates, the tonal peaks are—except for the peak at 800 Hz—suppressed. In addition, the downstream (Fig. 9c) and upstream-only (Fig. 9d) configurations, which include a QWR-cell directly underneath the propeller’s center, show an increase in tonal noise—particularly for the 4th and 5th blade passing frequency (BPF). For example, if no QWR is present underneath the rotating propeller, the effects observed in the full-QWR case are suppressed. That confirms in the authors’ minds that—as suspected—the increased tonal peaks observed in the case of a full-QWR configuration are due to a local hydrodynamic effect. These results confirm that the cell directly underneath the propeller center contributes the most to said local hydrodynamic effect.

Fig. 9 Spectra for the different QWR-cell configurations in the frequency range for which the QWR cells were optimized. Results $U_\infty = 30 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, 6000 RPM and microphone at $\theta = 90^\circ$

In Fig.10, the directivity is quantified for the cases of the flat-plate-center configuration (grey circles connected by a thick grey line) and flat-plate-blade (red squares connected by a thick red line)—both cases are compared to the full-flat-plate configuration (finely-dotted black line). The directivity patterns are slightly different for each case

(Fig. 10a), particularly for the flat-plate-center. In addition, the flat-plate-center and flat-plate-blade configurations show a tendency for noise increase towards downstream positions. Moreover, in Fig. 10b, the overall sound pressure level difference is shown as a function of the polar angle θ . One observes that the flat-plate-blade configuration yields the most significant outcome for noise reduction (about 1.0 dB) in the investigated polar-angle range. Covering only the central region—i.e., using the flat-plate-center configuration—yields noise reduction at some polar angles. However, most angles show no significant noise reduction or even noise increase. Indeed, in the flat-plate-center, noise reduction does not exceed 0.5 dB—in the investigated polar-angle range. Moreover, one infers that said local hydrodynamic effect is not only caused by the blade-QWR interaction at the closest position (central QWR) but also by all the other QWR-cells on the blade path. Therefore, one confirms the occurrence of the earlier-proposed local hydrodynamic effect.

Fig. 10 Overhead array directivity for flat-plate-center and flat-plate-blade configurations. (a) OSPL directivity. (b) Comparison between full-flat-plate case and flat-plate-center (grey line), flat-plate-blade (red line) configurations, respectively.

In Fig. 11, two configurations are compared, namely, the upstream-only (red squares connected by a thick red line) and the downstream-only (grey circles connected by a thick gray line). One observes, in Fig. 11a, which contains flat-plate data (finely-dotted black line) for reference, that in terms of θ , the overall directivity is not significantly affected by either configuration. In Fig. 11b, one notices that as a function of the polar angle, θ , the configuration of the QWR-cells influences the directivity. Moreover, in the case of the downstream-only configuration in the full angle range, recorded sound-pressure levels slightly decrease with respect to the flat-plate reference case. While, in the range $100^\circ < \theta < 135^\circ$, one observes an increase in recorded sound-pressure levels for the upstream-only configuration.

Fig. 11 Overhead array directivity for the upstream-only and downstream-only configurations. (a) OSPL directivity. (b) Comparison between full-flat-plate case and upstream-only (red line), downstream-only (grey line) configurations.

4. Flat-plate-blade QWR-cell configuration comparison to metal-foam sample

Based on the results discussed in §III.B.3 and §III.B.5, the authors determined that the flat-plate-blade QWR-cell configuration is the most effective of the ones which were considered, in terms of tonal peaks reduction (Fig. 9b) and overall noise abatement (Fig. 10b).

To make a general judgment about the efficacy of QWRs as a noise-mitigating strategy, the flat-plate-blade QWR-cell configuration is compared to a commonly-applied noise-mitigation material: a porous material; viz., a metal foam (§II.C.2).

In Fig. 12, recorded sound-pressure levels (at $\theta = 90^\circ$) for the metal foam (solid grey line) are compared to the flat-plate-blade QWR-cell configuration (solid red line), and (as a reference) the full-flat-plate (finely-dotted black line). In the low-frequency range (1st and 2nd BPF), the metal-foam results exhibit higher tonal peaks (Fig. 12a). However, as can be appreciated in Fig. 12b, for the mid-range (4th to 8th BPF), both tonal and broadband noise is in the case of the metal foam significantly reduced—compared to both the flat-plate-blade configuration and the flat-plate reference.

In Fig. 13, results are presented in terms of OSPL in the polar-angle range $40^\circ \leq \theta \leq 135^\circ$. One observes that, compared to the flat-plate-center QWRs and the flat plate reference case, the metal foam causes an increase in OSPL across the full range of considered polar angles in the experiments. This effect is most pronounced in the $80^\circ < \theta < 100^\circ$ range. In contrast, in the flat-plate-blade QWR configuration, one sees a general OSPL decrease in the polar angle range considered.

5. Azimuthal-directivity measurements

The side array was used to investigate the influence of QWR-cell configuration on azimuthal directivity. This section focuses on the results for two QWR configurations and the porous material. The considered QWR-configurations are

Fig. 12 Noise spectra of the propeller with QWR (flat-plate-blade configuration) and porous metal. Results for $U_\infty = 30 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, 6000 RPM and $\theta = 90^\circ$ microphone.

Fig. 13 Overhead array directivity for the flat-plate-blade and porous metal mitigators. (a) OSPL directivity. (b) Comparison between full-flat-plate case and flat-plate-blade (red line), porous metal (grey line) configurations.

the flat-plate-blade (Fig. 2c) and down-stream-only) configurations, respectively.

In Fig. 14, the results obtained with the in-the-above-paragraph-alluded-to three noise-mitigation strategies are shown. The flat-plate blade and downstream-only QWR-cell configurations are indicated with grey squares and red triangles, respectively. Black diamonds are used to show the results obtained with the metal-foam sample. Results obtained with a rigid wall (black dotted line) instead of noise mitigation materials are also shown for comparison.

In the range $46^\circ \leq \phi \leq 120^\circ$ one observes (see Fig.14a) an increase in OSPL for all three cases with respect to the flat-plate reference. This increase is most pronounced in the range $40^\circ < \phi < 90^\circ$ (upstream of the propeller). Downstream (i.e. $\phi \geq 90^\circ$), this increase in OSPL is less pronounced. Moreover, for $\phi \geq 120^\circ$ the results for all three noise-mitigation cases tend to the flat-plate reference.

In Fig. 14b, the difference in OSPL with respect to the flat-plate reference case is shown. One observes that the

flat-plate-blade configuration (grey squares) generally engenders the smallest increase in OSPL, i.e., with respect to the reference case. On this basis, the authors will qualify the flat-plate-blade configuration as the best of the two considered here.

Fig. 14 Side array directivity for QWR flat-plate-blade, donstream-only and the porous metal; full-flat-plate for comparison. (a) OSPL directivity. (b) Comparison between full-flat-plate case and each configuration.

IV. Conclusion

The presently-reported study investigated the effect of noise-mitigating materials placed underneath a propeller on emitted noise and its directivity. In particular, the impact of various configurations of band-stop quarter-wavelength resonators (QWRs) and a single broadband metal-foam absorber on the noise emitted by a propeller system was investigated.

The directivity was examined using two microphone arrays, one placed overhead and the other positioned on the right-hand side of the propeller (in the stream-wise direction). Our analysis shows that, for small clearance, the effectiveness of the QWRs depends on their configuration. Indeed, the findings indicate that for a clearance of 5 mm, there is a hydrodynamic interaction between the blade tips and the QWR tubes. Said hydrodynamic interaction leads to a resonance which significantly influences the emitted noise. Said surmised resonance amplifies the emitted propeller-induced tonal noise, especially on the higher harmonics.

Therefore, removing the QWR-cell from the region directly beneath the propeller and replacing it with a rigid wall while applying QWR-cells everywhere else on the instrumentation surface yields the best noise-abatement performance. Indeed, applying QWRs in the optimal configuration yielded notable reductions in tonal and broadband noise in the mid-frequency range. In terms of directivity, changing the position of the QWRs more upstream or downstream affected the polar directivity patterns of the propeller noise. However, the presence of both the QWRs and the metal foam negatively affected the azimuthal directivity.

In addition, the optimal QWR configuration was compared to a metal-foam broadband absorber. The porous metal exhibited higher tonal peaks in the low-frequency range than the optimally-configured QWRs. The data indicate that applying QWRs in their optimal configuration is, at least in these experiments, the more successful noise abatement strategy.

Appendix

A. Boundary layer establishment and characterization

The characteristics of the boundary layer were measured (in the absence of the propeller) in the propeller's plane using hot-wire anemometry. Characterization was done with 105 evenly spaced points (z coordinate; normal to the wind tunnel's main flow axis). To perform these measurements the DANTEC's StreamLine Pro CTA, with a 55P15 single-wire probe acquiring for 20 s at a 2^{16} Hz-acquisition frequency, was used.

The data were fitted with Spalding and Cole's equations, using a simplified version of the technique presented in [25]. This fitting procedure allowed the determination of the main parameters of the boundary layer: Considering x as the distance between the tripping device and the propeller plane, ν the kinematic viscosity of air, and U_∞ the flow speed, the boundary layer thickness δ is the position where $u(z) = 0.99U_\infty$, determined by the hot-wire experiment. The boundary layer displacement thickness δ_1 and momentum thickness δ_2 can be determined with the results of the hot-wire anemometry. The form factor comes from those parameters: $H = \delta_1/\delta_2$.

In Fig. 15a fitting results are shown, which were obtained with tripping thickness $h = 8$ mm and $U_\infty = 30 \pm 0.66$ m \cdot s $^{-1}$. The following boundary layer parameters were found from the results: boundary layer thickness $\delta = 102.5$ mm, form factor $H = 1.27$, Clauser parameter $\beta = 0.2$, Reynolds number for x coordinate $Re_x = 7.29 \times 10^6$ and Reynolds number for the momentum thickness $Re_{\delta_2} = 22370$.

Fig. 15 Turbulent boundary layer characteristics at the propeller plane. a) Fitting of the data points (microscale) with Spalding and Cole's equations. b) Turbulence intensity distribution.

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